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“BLACK LEGEND” AS A TOOL OF THE GEOPOLITICAL STRUGGLE IN THE SIXTEENTH CENTURY AND ITS INTERPRETATION TODAY: THE DENIGRATION OF THE ENEMY-COUNTRY AND THE STRATEGY OF “DEMONIZING” THE ENEMY

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Abstract

Aim. To comprehensively study the real historical events that took place in 1562–1567 in Spanish Florida, when Spain was vilified by its enemies, while the illegal actions of the French themselves were presented in a different light to the society of France and Europe.

Methodology. The following important works formed the basis of this research: Bennett’s publications, including the memoirs of the French who participated in the events; the letters from the kings of Spain and France, as well as Spanish ambassadors in France; the memoirs of the contemporaries of those events and published manuscripts. The research was conducted using the methods of comparison, historical analysis, and expert assessment.

Results. The history of the struggle between Spain and France on the shores of modern Florida and in the West Indies in 1565 allows drawing a historical parallel between the development of manipulative methods of influence today and the methods of denigrating the enemy 450 years ago. Both then and today the “image of the enemy” is used to justify any illegal actions. The examples from 450 years ago show how bribery and the economic incentives of the “fifth column” of traitors within the country can cause irreparable damage to an entire state.

Research implications. The historic examples show and reveal the myths about Spain, as well as the methods and scale of the information war aimed at creating an image of the enemy for the society of France and European countries. A comparative analysis of these historical events of 1563–1565 and contemporary technologies of information warfare sets a prospect for further studies.

Keywords: Black Legend, Spanish Florida, French Florida, pirates West-India, Jean Ribault, Menendez, La Carolina, information war, enemy image, fifth column, mythological model, demonization strategy

«ЧЕРНАЯ ЛЕГЕНДА» КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ГЕОПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ БОРЬБЫ В XVI ВЕКЕ И ЕЁ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ СЕГОДНЯ: ОЧЕРНЕНИЕ СТРАНЫ-ВРАГА И СОВРЕМЕННАЯ СТРАТЕГИЯ «ДЕМОНИЗАЦИИ»

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Аннотация

Цель. Всесторонне изучить реальные исторические события, происходившие в 1562–1567 гг. на Земле испанской Флориды, когда Испания была очернена врагами, а незаконные действия самих французов были представлены в ином свете обществу Франции и Европы.

Процедура и методы. Для исследования были отобраны важные работы: публикации Беннетта, в т. ч. мемуары французов, участвовавших в событиях, письма королей Испании и Франции, испанских послов во Франции, воспоминания современников тех событий и опубликованные рукописи. В работе использованы методы сравнения, исторического анализа, экспертной оценки.

Результаты. Проведена историческая параллель между событиями развития техники манипулятивных методов воздействия сегодня и методами работы по очернению врага 450 лет назад. Показана история борьбы между Испанией и Францией на берегах современной Флориды и в Вест-Индии в 1565 г. И тогда, и сегодня «образ врага» распространяется, чтобы оправдать любые противоправные действия. На примерах 450-летней давности видно, как подкуп и экономические стимулы «пятой колонны» предателей внутри страны могут нанести непоправимый ущерб всему государству.

Теоретическая и/или практическая значимость. На реальных примерах рассмотрены и раскрыты мифы об Испании. Показаны методы ведения и масштаб информационной войны, направленный на создание образа врага для общества Франции и европейских стран. Проведён сравнительный анализ исторических событий 1563–1565 гг. и современных технологий информационной войны.

Ключевые слова: чёрная легенда, испанская Флорида, французская Флорида, пираты Вест-Индии, Жан Рибо, Менендес, Ла Каролина, информационная война, образ врага, пятая колонна, мифологическая модель, стратегия демонизации

Introduction

Although the term «Black Legend» was used by the French writer Arthur Levy in his work *Napoléon Intime* in 1893 A.D., and Emilia Pardo Bazan y de La Roi-Figueroa¹ wrote the work «Spain yesterday and today. The end of the legend» in 1899 A.D., but it became widespread in the 20th century when in 1914, Julian Juderias y Loyot already ac-

cused all European thinkers that «they were completely purposefully involved in slandering the Spanish nation as a historical community» and that «everything negative said about Spain and the Spaniards are slander and malice of all Europe» [1, p. 232].

However, the term «Black Legend» best fits the «defamatory propaganda» that was waged against Spain and the Spaniards in the XVI century by Italy, France, England, and the Netherlands.

In this investigation we considered the events which took place opposed both sides

¹ Emilia, condesa de Pardo Bazán. Spanish writer. In: *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Emilia-condesa-de-Pardo-Bazan> (accessed: 8.03.2020).

of the Atlantic Ocean. The main point is that the French crown used «slandering propaganda» («negative propaganda») among the French in the relationship to Spain to cover her own pirate's activities against Spain and Portugal.

Outright lies, hiding of their illegal actions, and inflating events in the spirit of modern «information war» high probability led to the justification and unrestrained growth of piracy between the Old World and New World in the 16th century and flowed into the 17th century. Studying one of the most striking examples in history from 1562–1567, we fulfilled, according to Soviet scholar Fursov A. I., the task of «historians as detectives of world history», relying on primary sources and documents from different countries that became available to us in the era of the technical revolution, and compared it with the current state of things in the vast modern information struggle.

The global reach of society by slanderous propaganda led the high intensity of hatred of Spain, which has made the image of Spain as the main threat to other European countries very permanent, and this has led to the existing fear of European society from Spain. The propaganda of the enemy countries told about Spanish laziness, which was the result of the belligerence, pride. All of these was an obstacle to the development of society and trade and industry, according to French enlighteners. [1, p. 232].

Russian scholar E. Yurchik claims that writers from Italy, such as Petrarch, Valla, and Boccaccio, began to portray the Spaniards very unpleasantly because Spain was becoming a dangerous rival for Italy. Italian philosophers represented the Spaniards as semi-Saracens and stated that the Christianity of the Spanish people was very doubtful, and every Spaniard was not of pure blood, but had the blood of Jews and Muslims and said that the Spaniards were more barbarians or semi-barbarians. And all these efforts were aimed at cultivating the image of the Spaniards as outsiders in Europe.

The image of Spaniards as scarecrows existed in many countries, even far from Spain (for example, in Russia) from 1492 to the present. Countries that were enemies of Spain needed this image to show the public examples of horror (the Inquisition), callousness (the killing of thousands of natives), and plundering of peoples (sending gold and silver to Spain and destroying the Aztec, Mayan, and Inca civilizations). It was very profitable for them to hide their crimes, to justify their piracy and violence, to say that their illegal actions were only a step of revenge against Spain, but in fact, these steps covered real attacks, robberies, murders of hundreds and thousands of people around the world and were just a justification for the war for their interests in different countries.

As said E. Yurchik in the interview if we look at the other side, we will find that Spain has been under the pressure of information wars for more than 500 years and has suffered humiliation from European enemies. And these situations increased during anti-Spanish behavior in different countries at different times (this was in Italy, France, England, the Netherlands, the United States, etc.) and depended on the political and economic courses of the aristocracy and business in these countries. An example is the Netherlands, where the book «The apologize or defense of the noblest Prince William, by the grace of God, Prince of Orange... against the proclamation and edict, published by the King of Spain...» was published in 1580 in French, accusing the Spanish king Charles V (Charles I) of aggression and tyranny as said E. Yurchik in the interview.

E. Yurchik said that when Spain appeared on the international arena all enemies used, again and again, the same methods, techniques, and the same stereotypes: enemies told about Spain as a neighbor which haven't any good characteristics and that Spaniards are fanatics and have non-Christian representations of the world and are the enemy for all Europe. And Spaniards is they are lazy, proud, arrogant, and their main occupation is war.

Antonio Perez¹, the former private secretary of Philip II, who had access to many state secrets, as befits a renegade, once in France, writes his «Relaciones» [13] which published in 1598, where he creates the image of Philip II, embodying all the vices of the Spanish nation. Unfortunately, these attacks achieved their goal – all generations in Europe grew up and had very real forms of false ideas about Spain and the Spaniards. This lie was very strong, and even the intelligentsia in Spain repented of their history [1, c. 233], although Spain was no different from other countries, and sometimes the Spaniards were more humanists than other Nations as said E. Yurchik.

Thus, today we can show the course of history and how to create various myths of the image of the enemy from Spain in contrast to the supposedly more enlightened Europe. This reminds us of the situation with the creation of myths about Russia described in the book of V. E. Baghdasaryan about anti-Russian historical myths [2].

We have seen the wrong exculpatory policy of Spain in relation to the hyped false and aggressive policy of France when the French accused the Spaniards of anything to cover up their own crimes and murders. Also, France itself kept silent about its economic interests during the colonization of Florida under the guise of supposedly peaceful settlers, who quickly turned to pirate attacks on Spanish possessions in the New World.

We showed the «Fifth column» from traitors of Spain who preferred their enrichment and growing personal accounts instead of serving their Motherland.

We believe that will be a more comfortable presentation of material if we follow the next steps during describing events:

- information attack;
- the event which took place;
- motivations and own goal;
- economic reasons for an event;
- main aspects.

¹ Antonio Perez. In: *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Antonio-Perez> (accessed: 8.03.2020).

Analysis of historical events of 1562–1567 on the land of Spanish Florida

Information attack

The allegation of the massacre of peaceful French Huguenots, including men, women, and children, in a settlement on Florida land at Fort La Carolina by the Adelantado (Spanish governor) of Florida², Pedro Menendez de Aviles, and his troops [6, p. 118–122].

This story was written by the cartographer and artist Jacques Le Moyne de Morgues³ [6, p. 2–7], who escaped with the head of La Florida expedition René Goulaine de Laudonnière [6, p. 18] from the captured Fort La Carolina [6, p. 162]. Le Moyne wrote that this story was allegedly written by an eyewitness to the events of an unknown (his name is not given) French sailor from Dieppe [6, p. 118]. This sailor was allegedly in the second group with Ribault and surrendered to the Spaniards a few days after the murder of Ribault's Huguenot soldiers on the «Cape of carnage». Strangely, the source doesn't even have a first or last name, but we should trust it as the current unproven «highly likely».

Events 1562–1565

French fort La Carolina (near the modern city of Sant Augustin) was captured by Spanish soldiers on the coast of Spanish Florida (Pascua de Florida), which was discovered by conquistador Ponce de Leon [1, c. 61; 3, c. 320–341; 11], his navigator Anton de Alaminos during the expedition [12] in 1513 [10].

Spaniards really killed 450 French soldiers under the leadership of Jean Ribault but kept the lives for all Frenchmen who were Catholics' which with women and children from Fort La Carolina which were sent to Havana by ships of Spain.

² Adelantado. In: *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/search?query=Adelantado> (accessed: 8.03.2020).

³ Daniels G. C. Le Moyne's Florida Indians. In: *The New World*. Available at: <http://thenewworld.us/le-moynes-florida-indians> (accessed: 8.03.2020).

The motives and real purposes of France

The purpose of the propaganda was to seek to consolidate French society since France has divided into two warring camps – the Huguenots and the Catholics, who waged religious war for many years inside France.

The second goal was to conceal and justify their actions in violating the Treaty of Cateau-Cambrésis 1559¹ and to justify their French piracy in the New World, which was funded by the French crown.

The third goal was to justify the illegal seizure of land in Spanish Florida and the occupation of territories strategically located near the Bahamas channel as a unique route for all Spanish ships coming from the New World.

Economy reasons for an event

There was full control for the routes of Spanish ships with gold and silver from New World in case of successful founded the settlement and established of French Florida. In this case, Frenchmen could take the money as toll and have the possibility of sinking all ships of Spain in the case of disobeying [17].

So, if the defense of the Fort La Carolina by French Huguenots was successful there was a strategic position in Florida, and France could take the money for toll without occupied territories of natives' people and fights with them.

Also, this side was a very nice place for piracy bases for all types of ships that rob and carried on the illegal trade and shared half of the loot with the French crown.

Also, this point was a very convenient point to organize rebellions in West-India by black slaves and disaffected local leaders (caciques) for the purpose of bringing the administration of the West-India under the jurisdiction of France.

Florida was the strategic point to find the settlement of French Huguenots on the territory of Spanish Florida.

¹ Treaty of Cateau-Cambrésis. In: *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/search?query=Treaty+of+Cateau%E2%80%91Cambr%C3%A9sis> (accessed: 8.03.2020).

France needed Florida as a strategic base for an attack on the trade ships of Spain which led from the New World and the point to conduct piracy activity. If this point could function so this led to control under all Atlantic coast from Florida to Newfoundland and declaring territory as territories of France in 1535, Jacques Cartier (French: Jacques Cartier, Bret. Jakez Karter), who discovered the country Canada and declared it to belong to France².

What's happened really?

France broke the peace accord that was developed in the Treaty of Cateau-Cambrésis 1559. This was done under pressure from Pope Pius IV (Giovanni Angelo Medici)³, who was at war with Spain in Italy. The French landed twice on the coast of Florida. The first time France did it in 1552 A.D. and founded Fort Charlesfort and the second time it was in 1564 A.D. when French Huguenots founded fort La Carolina.

Spain sent several ships to Florida under the command of the Adelantado of Florida, Pedro Menendez de Aviles.

France sent 7 ships with 600 soldiers led by Viceroy of the French Florida Jean Ribault in 1565 to fight the Spanish and supported a new Fort that was built in 1564 there and was named La Carolina. The French expedition consisted of 600 men, 52 captains, 7 Huguenot priests [7, p. 60] and women, artisans, and others [6, p. 111].

Spaniards and French fleets reached the beach of Florida simultaneously on 25 August 1565. The Frenchman had more fast and better ships, they had a nice Fort La Carolina and a big garrison. There were more soldiers of France than Spaniards.

Soon the Spaniards' ships entered in the water near the La Carolina and the enemies saw each other but the Spaniards left this place without a fight.

² Jacques-Cartier. In: *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Jacques-Cartier>. (accessed: 8.03.2020).

³ Pius IV. In: *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Pius-IV>. (accessed: 8.03.2020).

6 September 1565 the French soldiers embarked on the 4 ships and followed to a fleet of Spain to try to find them. They wanted to kill all of Spaniards. But a hurricane sank all French ships 10 September 1565 [9, p. 149]. Both fleets were wrecked [9, p. 149]. One ship from seven was found in September 2015 near the coast of Florida¹.

In this time Menendez and 150 the Spaniards made march by the land and attacked fort La Carolina 12 September 1565. The fort was captured in the result of several moments and mistakes of Frenchmen [9, p. 149] and by guide Frenchman Jean François. The Spaniards killed all men and kept the life for women and children under 15 years. 70 people were spared and except fifty or sixty who jumped from the walls of the fort and took refuge in the woods from which the Adelantado had come [8, p. 62]. During the attack were only 150 Spaniards included without any support ships under the head of Menendez.

The aborigines found the first group of 127 French people who were on the inlet and immediately told about it for Menendez. Frenchmen offer 50.000 (fifty thousand) ducats if Menendez spared all their lives. «But Menendez said that they belonged to the new religion, he considered them enemies. He had a war of blood and fire with them, and he would wage it with all cruelty against those he found on that sea or land where he was viceroy and captain general for his king» [8, p. 66]. The Spaniards tied up the surrendered French by 10 men and took them behind the dunes and stabbed them [8, p. 67]. The Spaniards killed 111 from 127 Frenchmen every one [21] but excluded persons who had catholic faith [8, p. 63–68].

12 October 1565 native people found the second group which was about 200 French soldiers under head Jean Ribault who was the Viceroy of French Florida. Menendez

killed 134 Frenchmen with Ribault [21] everybody excluded people with catholic faith [6, p. 111; 8, p. 69–73].

1 November was found in the third group by Indians. This group is surrounded and taken prisoner and all captures from this group and La Carolina sent to Havana [8, p. 74–78].

There were the memories of cartographer and painter Le Moyne which wrote about Spaniards as very crude people and he describes some cruelties during the fights and after. Many of his describe stories were taken from the Frenchman was taken prisoner by the Spaniards. It was only words and emotions. There was not describing the fact that was kept alive 50 women and children and were surrounded and kept lives for 100 French soldiers from the third party which was detected by aborigines and surrounded [8, p. 75].

The covert mission of Frenchmen in Florida

When the fort La Carolina was captured Spaniards was found the box in the room of Jean Ribault. There were documents there. And in one of them was written that admiral of France Gaspard Coligny ordered for Ribault executed special mission. The mission had the plan to defend the Fort from the Spaniards and send Frenchmen in all parts of West-Indies by ships and release all black slaves to raise the rebellions for the purpose to capture lands of Spaniards and kill all of them. The goal of this raising of rebellions was to capture the lands and forts of Spaniards by France fleet and to create a government of Frenchmen and let black men, mulattoes, and mestizos take the Huguenot religion and began the pirates' wars and trade between France and new lands which must take from the Spaniards. So, there were the orders from the admiral of France – Gaspard Coligny to Viceroy of the French Florida Jean Ribault to mass murder and expulsion of Spaniards from their territories in the West Indies, Florida, and other territories. Many people saw this document [8, p. 222].

¹ La Trinité, le navire du corsaire Jean Ribault, émerge des flots en Floride. In: Lire le journal. Culture. Available at: <https://www.lefigaro.fr/culture/2016/12/01/03004-20161201ARTFIG00232-latrinite-emerge-des-flots-en-floride.php> (accessed: 8.03.2020).

The cheat of the society about peaceful settlements and the mission of Huguenots

Menendez and his soldiers found a little coffer of documents that Jean Ribault, the general of the French troops, had in his room [8, p. 207]. So, there were the orders from Admiral Gaspard Coligny to Viceroy of the French Jean Ribault and for the founder of fort La Carolina – René de Goulaine de Laudonnière to protect fort La Carolina and held the coast of Florida and did not allow the Spaniards to harm them [8, p. 205–207]. So, we can see that France announce war to the Spaniards.

Before arriving in Florida from France, several Frenchmen raised a toast to the heads of Pedro Menendez and his men, whom the French called «Spanish pigs», and French soldiers said they want to hang them in their shipyards and the shipyards of Spanish ships: «I drink to the heads of Pedro Menéndez and his men, who are Spanish pigs! We shall punish them by hanging them from the yards of their ships and our own, and they shall not come back to look for us in this, our land!» [8, p. 75].

Cover own crime in 1562–1567

Frenchmen disembarked in 1564 and built the fort La Carolina and immediately shown their plans.

From 4 to 10 September 1564 the ship under the head of very famous French pirate Bourdet Jean Bontemps [15, p. 33–34] visited Huguenots in La Carolina [14, p. 265]. This ship did not participate in the expedition and Bontemps was privateer and back to France from the piracy voyage in West-India which took place every year. He had a plan to visit the previous fort of Frenchmen in Florida – Charlesfort, which was left by Huguenots in 1563 not far from La Carolina [7, p. 53]. And he had news to Laudonnière about the expedition of Ribault. There were several sailors and two carpenters left in Huguenots colony from the ship of Capitan Bourdet Jean Bontemps [14, p. 265].

1563. King Charles IX wrote the letter about captain Bourdet where he calls the pirate Bourdet Jean Bontemps «my captain»

who keeps in touch between Florida and France and brings news from there about the creation of Charlesfort [6, p. 129].

From this letter, we understand that the king was well aware of the piracy and construction of an illegal French settlement in Florida in both 1562 and 1564.

Pirate captain Bourdet robbed the Spain territories since 1550th years. He took place in piracy, illegal trade of negroes from Africa, kidnapping, etc. in the New World on the territories of Spain.

In 1559, the Huguenot Frenchman Bourdet Jean Bontemps and Jean-Martin Cotes attacked Santa Marta, Cartagena, and ravaged them receiving in their robber attacks 100,000 pesos and as it turned out constantly went to rob and illegal traded with Hispaniola and other territories of Spanish New World every year. He changed the Catholic faith to the Huguenot's faith in 1562 [8, p. 167].

After he visited many officers and sailors from the new settlement La Carolina in Florida went to pirates' voyages from Florida to West-India. [14, p. 265].

6 (or 9) December 1564. 60 Huguenots took two ships which were built in the colony and sailed to the south from fort La Carolina [9, p. 146] to capture Spanish ships with gold and silver from New World. They reached Cuba and captured several Spain ships [9, p. 145–146].

Huguenots-pirates from Florida returned to Fort La Carolina on March 25 with captured the Spanish brigantine [14, p. 266].

Soon they began again to plunder and attack Spanish ships at sea and captured the Governor of Havana. The Governor offered a large ransom for himself and his two sons. The French sent one son to the Governor's wife and waited for the money. The woman understood her husband's secret plan, which the governor told his son in his ear when he was alone with him. And the ships and the soldiers from Cuba surrounded pirates and attacked them. 26 French pirates-Huguenots out of 60 withdrew from the battle and returned to La Carolina. Six Frenchmen were

killed, and others were captured and sold as galley slaves. The pirates which back to La Carolina in Florida were noble Fourneau, Teen de Genovese, La Croix, Navigator, and sailors [6, p. 108–109].

Only after this piracy attack administration in West India and king Phillip II understood the very big danger from the settlement of French Huguenots in Florida. King Philip II decided to find the constant settlement and remove France from the Florida coast. The Queen-Mother Catherine Medici of French king Charles IX wrote the letter in 1566 to Philip II about punish Pedro Menendez for killing French Huguenots in Florida and the ambassador forced to excused for Menendez actions [6, p. 179].

There were explanations of the actions of Adelantado by the Spanish Ambassador in France on the French crown's demand to punish Menendez [6, p. 131]:

– The French who settled in Spanish Florida were not regular soldiers but were armed pirates.

– The French greatly outnumbered the Spaniards of Menendez (French soldiers of Ribault and René de Goulaine de Laudonnière from the first expedition).

– There were no ships to send prisoners (all the ships were destroyed by the storm), and there were no food supplies to feed everyone [7, p. 60], and there was a clear threat of starvation. There was a threat of an Indian uprising and the capture of Fort La Carolina and then the Indians and the French would kill all the Spaniards (which happened two years later – during the revenge expedition of captain Gourgues [6, p. 202–227]).

– All the women and children of the settlers from fort La Carolina and 100 people who surrendered on 1 November 1565 were rescued

– All the Catholics were also spared.

*The activities of «Fifth column»
in 1565–1566*

There was a very interesting work of the «Fifth column», which we can observe from the evidence during the struggle of the

Spanish and French in Florida. Adelantado Pedro Menendez de Aviles [8, p. 165] was shocked by the actions of rich people in Hispaniola when he tried to organize a fight against French pirates. There were enemies within the West-India who were traitors to the interests of Spain.

Menendez found that the pirate-privateer Jean Bontemps many years since 1550th visited Hispaniola and Puerto-Rico to illegal trade by goods and black slaves, especially in 1564–1565.

Menendez kept the garrison about 50 arquebusiers and four good bronze artillery pieces, to protect the town Puerto-de-Plata on the Hispaniola Island [8, p. 165].

Soon the 4 ships of piracy under the head of Jean Bontemps tried to disembark to Puerto-de-Plata but they were repulsed from town by the garrison under the head of captain Aguirre.

It was a big surprise that no one helped soldiers except for only 5 volunteers. And Adelantado Menendez investigated this question. He discovered that the French pirate Jean Bontemps (Jean Botempt) very often conducted illegal trade with the citizens of this city with their consent [8, p. 165]. They traded in gold, silver, pearls, sugar, leather, etc. Many wealthy citizens believed that Menendez closed this channel of trade to enrich the citizens.

But the main point was that the wealthiest man in the city, Francisco de Ceballos, each traded more actively with the French, Portuguese, and other pirates, especially with Jean Bontemps. This Francisco de Ceballos owned a factory, cattle, and other wealth. Soon de Ceballos sent false reports to the Supreme court of Hispaniola that captain Aguirre and his soldiers were unruly and a threat to the city [8, p. 165–166].

The Supreme Court of Hispaniola Island asked King Philip II to replace captain Aguirre Francisco with de Ceballos, and appoint Ceballos as caretaker of the tower, and the king granted his request. Menendez wrote afterward that Francisco de Ceballos was conducting illegal trade with pirates from

France, Portugal, and England, who often visited the New World without permission and first plundered and then sold what they plundered, and this was contrary to the edicts of king Philip II [8, p. 165–166].

Menendez wrote that Francisco de Ceballos always avoids the court because he married the sister of Royal Judge (Licenciado) Lucas Vazquez de Ayllon [8, p. 165] and had family relations with members of the Supreme Court.

This was a personal hatred and dislike since in 1561 it was because Adelantado's position (Spanish governor) was transferred from De Ayllon's family to Menendez. This was done by king Philip II due to the delay and refusal of the son of De Ayllon to organize the settlement in Florida.

From that moment personal hatred and greed made Francisco de Ceballos a personal enemy of Menendez and at the same time a traitor to the interests of Spain. Francisco de Ceballos was outraged by the king's decision to appoint Menendez at the position as Adelantado but hid his hatred. He gradually began to harm and destroy the «fruits of the Spanish crown's labor». But he did it in secret, causing irreparable damage to Menendez and the Spaniards.

For example, when the ships of Menendez's nephew, Pedro Menendez Marquez, passed through Puerto de Plata to Florida with a fleet from Spain (Asturias and Vizcaya), Francisco de Ceballos wrote to the Adelantado to send him some ships and he would load them with supplies and cattle and many things, for the port was suitable and had supplies. The Adelantado, thinking this to be true, sent six of his ships there. Ceballos detained some of them until they were riddled with worms and became unseaworthy. The others sailed because he did not load them, and the one he did load went down on the second day after leaving the Harbor [8, p. 166].

At the same time, the traitor to the Spanish nation did not suffer any punishment, since the Supreme court of Hispaniola was headed by a man who had direct family ties with Ceballos and Don Cristybal Colyn

(Don Cristybal Colyn) and mutual ties and friendship bound all families [8, p. 167].

This is how the «Fifth column» of traitors of Spain operated, filling their pockets with illegal trade with pirates and preventing the eradication of French piracy in the Caribbean in 1565–1570.

Conclusion

Thus, we analyzed the original documents and their translations about the events in Spanish Florida in 1562–1567. We have seen how the propaganda machine of France worked, justifying its illegal actions against Spain and waging a bloody and brutal war through its pirates. We have seen the French attempt to establish a strategic base in Florida to intercept and plunder Spanish ships.

Fort La Carolina was created to promote its plans to expand the French borders and replace the Spanish administration in the New World with the French one. To do this, it was planned to raise uprisings among the black population of the New World. Also, French piracy ships were sent to attack Spanish ships near the coast of the West-India, as well as other parts of the Spanish and Portuguese controls. French pirates committed piratical attacks, captured of Spaniards for ransom, and the plundering of Hispaniola and Cuba. All these were purposeful steps taken by the French from the territory of their new Fort La Carolina.

During and after successful military operations against the French Huguenots and their successful expulsion from their territories, the Spaniards were called barbarians, savages, murderers of unfortunate Huguenot settlers, etc. At the same time, the mass murder during acts of piracy, the destruction of cities and settlements, the burning of houses, violence against women, and other acts that were committed by French Huguenot pirates against the Spaniards and natives for many years throughout the sixteenth century were completely ignored. Their actions took place in all the overseas territories from Cuba, Puerto Rico, and other cities in the West Indies to New Spain.

Using «denigrating» the Spaniards as a nation and creating myths in negative style as «Black Legend» about them was the norm in literature and was often used by France, Netherlands, and England for the propaganda among their own population.

We can also see work the «Fifth column» of traitors, such as Francisco de Ceballos, who preferred to get rich for illegal trade with pirates of France and easily evaded responsibility through family connections in the judicial system.

This reminds us of today's events and today's history in many parts of the world.

The strategy of demonizing the enemy

Historically, the geopolitical situation has been determined by the fact that any country in the world needs to create an effective system to counteract the formation of its negative image on the world stage. Thus, conducting a large-scale information war has always been an effective tool for implementing the foreign policy of states that play an important role in the global international system.

Methods of manipulative influence have been actively used in the process of information warfare since ancient times. Manipulation in relation to politics and ideology is often understood as a process and result of the formation of a myth or a mythologized picture of the world in a special way. This definition is based on the mythological model of Roland Barthes, who defined myth as the basis of mass culture and ideology [4; 5].

The main mythologeme used during information warfare is the «enemy image» created by various manipulative methods¹ [19].

In contrast to the internal (positive) active image, which is created by the state itself, an external passive (and often negative) image is formed abroad as a kind of cognitive

pattern used a framework for the perception of the state by the world community.

This image is always evaluative in nature: it contains an assessment of the role of the state in the world arena. The «enemy image» is of particular interest. It is truly one of the most contradictory images, dominating to one degree or another during the existence of different systems of international relations.

The opponent's discreditation has been a common practice and a part of the informational warfare throughout history and it remains a very important element of modern domestic and foreign policy. This practice is based on the use of multiple communication strategies and methods of propaganda [18].

The focus of this article is the phenomenon of «demonization of the political or geopolitical enemy». This phenomenon is defined as the utilization of the broad scope of the tools of manipulation of the mass consciousness, which aim to identify the opponent as a «universal evil». This eventually leads to the «dehumanization» of the opponents whether those are represented by the political movements, political parties, military forces, or the entire polities [20].

Thus, it creates an opportunity to justify any hostile and ethically questionable actions against domestic as well as foreign rivals, and it provides a perfect tool for legitimization of such actions among your own supporters. While the typical or «regular» political discreditation usually intends to win the political competition or defeat the opponent in political discussion, the goal of «demonization strategy» is more radical. It aims at a total enemy's destruction, both morally and physically.

Nowadays, we can observe this practice in many countries, including recent cases in a number of nations. The use of «demonization strategy» also is evident in the way the Great Powers tend to demonize its geopolitical rivals to achieve its pragmatic goals [16].

This strategy still relies on the concept of «universal evil», historically fixed in the mass consciousness, as well as on such a

¹ PICA C.E. Manufacturing the enemy. From trade war to the pandemic spat, the impossible cohabitation of China and the US. In: Asia Power Watch. 2020. Available at: <https://asiapowerwatch.com/manufacturing-the-enemy-from-trade-war-to-the-pandemic-spat-the-impossible-cohabitation-of-china-and-the-us>. (accessed: 8.03. 2020).

basic characteristic of mass consciousness as religiosity. However, at the present stage, religiosity in secular society takes on a completely different, very unusual form.

It is no longer exclusively associated with traditional religion, since it has an inversion, transformed, sometimes even bizarre character. Modern mass consciousness (at least in Western society) is largely based on the values of the so-called secular «quasi-religions», a significant ideological ingredient of which is a fair amount of political mythology.

In North America and Europe, such a secular quasi-religion, with its axiological dogmas and moral imperatives, is democracy. In the eyes of the Western political elite, it is endowed with the status, if not absolute, then, in any case, the highest Good. Any political arrangement that does not quite fit the Western template of democracy is considered a global evil that must (sooner or later) be destroyed.

Although, it should be noted that the idea of democracy often acts not so much as a real ideal of freedom, as a convenient political screen that allows one to pursue one's geopolitical and economic interests. Thus, the Western political elite today begins to act as a special, almost priestly caste of this new quasi-religion, whose representatives endow themselves with the sacred right of the final and supreme interpretation of Good and Evil.

In fact, the Western political establishment today claims moral positions that the Vatican once lost. Now it is the collective West who determines what is the world's evil and what means should be used to fight it. At the same time, the religious and mythological properties of mass consciousness (uncritical and emotional perception of reality, submissive adherence to authorities, vivid xenophobia, lack of understanding of the deep causes of social processes, etc.) allow the ruling elite to successfully manipulate public opinion through controlled media to achieve their mercantile goals.

The strategy of demonizing the opponent is carried out using several special tech-

niques that involve the use of various both verbal and non-verbal instruments. It is useful to consider some of these techniques, which are currently most actively used.

The first technique can be conditionally designated as identifying the opponent with the biblical Evil or the devil. Western civilization has developed in the mainstream of the Christian religion for almost two thousand years. And if the basic moral norms of Christianity in the mass consciousness have long been overthrown, then biblical archetypes and symbols, paradoxically, still retain their significant influence on the worldview of the average person in the West.

The devil, as the personification of universal evil in the mass consciousness, is usually associated with such images as blood, violence, death, murder, debauchery, the torment of hell, torture, and suffering. The main psychological features of this character, unconsciously recognized by the consciousness of the individual, also have clearly negative content.

This is soullessness, cruelty, resourcefulness, cunning, deceit, fighting against God. Therefore, the repeated comparison of the political leader or the polity with the devil, as a rule, achieves its goal. This image in the mass consciousness takes on something sinister. And the emerging fear is one of the psychological sources of aggression.

Sooner or later, the consistent propaganda message to the audience reaches its goal, and the undesirable leader or entire country is transferred from the category of normal political opponents to the category of soulless villains, evil non-humans, and political monsters. From here there is only half a step to the «fair» call for reprisals against such a «villain». This is the hidden goal of manipulating the mass consciousness in the cases under consideration.

The second technological method of the demonization strategy under consideration is about opposing the political system, which includes an unwanted opponent, to the model proclaimed as the most moral and effective with its specific standards and values.

Another effective technique of the strategy of demonizing a political leader is the tactic of artificially criminalizing the opponent. Its main goal is to show a mass audience that an inconvenient leader or a polity is a global criminal.

All these techniques have been used with the impressive efficiency contributing to the creation of the «Black Legend».

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